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A report to inform the decision whether fast food outlets should
be banned near schools

(ES30083: Coursework)

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Childhood obesity has risen dramatically over the past decade with the obesity of 10–11-year-olds rising by 4.5 percentage points (Nuffield Trust, 2023). With 55% of obese children obese in adolescence and 80% of obese adolescents obese in adulthood (Simmonds et al., 2016) this trend creates significant health and economic impacts. Banning fast-food outlets near schools could help lower these impacts.

The case for

Reduction in externalities

Several studies show a link between fast-food restaurants near schools and obesity. Davis and Carpenter (2009) found that in California a fast-food restaurant within 0.5 miles of a middle or high school increased the odds of a child being obese by 7%. Currie et al. (2010) furthered this, finding a 5.4% increase in the obesity rate of 9th graders in California when a fast-food outlet was located within 0.1 miles of a school. Libuy et al. (2023) expanded these studies into the UK finding that an additional fast-food restaurant within 800 metres of a school increased a child's BMI by 0.6% over the sample mean.

With obesity related health costs rising to £6.5 billion a year (Department for Health and Social Care Media Centre, 2023) and costing the economy £15.1 billion in lost productivity (Bradshaw and Dace, 2023) the papers show the policy could reduce obesity and lower these non-trivial externalities.

Protection of the vulnerable

Libuy et al. (2023) find that children with high levels of emotional dysregulation see an increase in BMI twice as large as their emotionally regulated peers when they have a fast-food outlet within 800 metres of their school or home. Further, Currie et al. (2010) support this finding with their paper suggesting that fast-food restaurants tempt those with self-control problems. Both these findings indicate that children who have a reduced ability to

make rational choices are disproportionately impacted by fast-food outlets near schools and thus introducing this policy helps to protect them.

Social Equality

Finally, Libuy et al. (2023) also find that the impact of fast-food restaurants is greatest on those of lower socio-economic status (SES). The ban would likely help to increase the health of children in lower SES families by more than those of more affluent ones leading to greater equality in outcomes such as life-expectancy.

The case against

Small and inconsistent relationships

There is no consensus on the link between fast-food outlets near schools and childhood obesity though. Anderson and Matsa (2011) for example find no relationship between restaurant consumption and obesity. Moreover, Giffiths et al. (2014) find little support that exposure to fast-food outlets increases the risk of childhood obesity and even call into question policy proposals to limit food outlets.

Even accepting a causal link, the estimates are small. Currie et al. (2010) find a significant relationship but explain only 0.5% of the increase in 9th grader obesity in the last 30-years. Davis and Carpenter's (2009) model explains just 5-10% of variation in youth weight and both papers focus on one US state and that may not be externally valid. Libuy et al. (2023) focus on the UK but also find that their point estimates are, by self-acknowledgement, small.

Implementation Challenges

The challenges of implementing such a ban too are considerable. The first of those challenges is defining the nature of the ban and if it affects only new or new and existing outlets. Moreover, there is little consensus on 'fast food' in academic literature and defining it

is an ambiguous task. A final question around what constitutes 'near' also remains. Is it half a mile? 1 mile? Or 2? Finding robust answers to these questions is difficult and time consuming on a policy that, as mentioned above, may simply not yield great benefit in the first place.

Unintended consequences

Unintended consequences are also a consideration. The policy may slow local economic growth and lead to job losses if outlets are forced to close. Further there may be social impacts as restaurants serving as community spaces close. Less tangible but equally important is the risk children may simply travel further for this food, increasing dangerous activities like busy road crossings.

The overall picture

Despite the lack of consensus, the policy does have merit. Point estimates are small but they are significant and despite this there is consensus around the impact on the vulnerable.

There are implementation challenges, but the literature does have some consensus such as using a rough guide of 0.5 miles as a threshold of 'near'.

A study proposal

To investigate the policy further a longitudinal study of individual students is recommended. This study is recommended for its ability to show time-varying effects and remove individual effects. The dependent variable is recommended to be BMI for its widespread use and ease of measurement. The independent variables should be whether there is a fast-food outlet within 400 metres of a school and the number of fast-food outlets within that radius. A 400-metre radius is used as this is the most recent policy proposal (Marsh S., 2018) however it could be expanded as desired, while using two explanatory variables, allows ministers to see

the difference in effect of banning all fast-food outlets or just stopping the opening of new ones.

Sample Selection and Data Collection

The sample should contain individual students across a range of school years up to an initial maximum of year 7 to ensure the study can run for a minimum of 6 years. 6 years is chosen to allow for child development and crossing from primary to secondary school. To ensure representation, students should be selected randomly from different ages, socio-economic backgrounds, regions, schools, genders, and ethnicities. The sample, and any proposed sub-group samples, should be sufficiently large to generate statistically significant results.

Measurements on BMI as well as individual characteristics, such as socio-economic status and school type, should be gathered from the sample. In addition, the number of fast-food outlets within 400 metres of the schools should be measured. Measurements should be re-taken every year for 6 years.

Estimation

A multivariate regression can be used to assess the impact:

$$BMI_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot Fast\ Food\ Outlet_{it}^{400} + \beta_2 \cdot Number\ of\ Fast\ Food\ Outlets_{it}^{400} + \beta_3 X_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where BMI_{it} is the BMI of individual i at time t , $Fast\ Food\ Outlet_{it}^{400}$ is a binary variable representing whether there is a fast food outlet within 400 metres of individual i 's school at time t , $Number\ of\ Fast\ Food\ Outlets_{it}^{400}$ is the number of fast-food outlets within 400 metres of individual i 's school at time t , X_{it} is a vector of control variables and ε_{it} is the error term.

From this analysis β_1 will show the impact of having at least 1 fast-food outlet near a school on BMI and β_2 will show the marginal impact of an increase of 1 fast food outlet near the school on BMI. Using this impact on BMI the impact on obesity can be estimated in a similar fashion to Currie et al. (2010). The controls also allow for subgroup analysis helping with implementation decisions such as to ban near primary or secondary schools.

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